

Social Factors of Stabilization of the Environmental Situation in Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The population of the world, which is becoming increasingly globalized and developing at a rapid pace, is facing a great environmental threat today. Climate change, fresh water shortage, air pollution, accumulation of industrial and household waste, soil erosion, depletion of the ozone layer and other factors are examples of such problems. Therefore, the international community has already recognized its sanctity and inviolability and is fighting for its comprehensive protection. Environmental safety is one of the most important issues today and in the future. In the course of our article, together with the analysis of the social factors of the stabilization of the ecological situation in our country, we will consider the international experience, the formation of an ecological safety system based on modern science, the issue of ecological safety at the level of state policy, covering the territory of the country on a high scale, and the experience of leading countries.

Keywords: Green space, coatings, Aral Sea, strategies, salt flats, saline, agro-industrial, desertification, Montreal Protocol, Bahrain, eco-friendly, nitrogen oxide, investment, media, Central Asia.

Enter

On September 11, 2023, the decree of the current President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030" was adopted. In this decree, the most important political document of the state focuses on the issue of ecology, in addition to providing health, which is the most necessary for a person in this life, protecting his health, providing social services and reducing poverty, and ensuring the well-being of the population through sustainable economic growth. In particular, in chapter 3, the introduction of the department of water resources conservation and environmental protection, or in paragraph 3.2, reforms on "Environmental protection" are presented. Based on these clauses, the national project "Green Space" aimed at achieving radical improvement of the ecological situation in the republic, elimination of problems that can have a negative impact on social life, stabilization of the ecological situation, prevention of negative effects of climate change, stabilization of the ecological situation in the island region, biological diversity - to ensure the preservation of diversity, to improve the quality of collection and processing of household waste, to take drastic measures to prevent atmospheric air pollution, to preserve its natural composition, through these tasks "Green Climate" and global ecological funds of biodiversity, climate change and soil degradation Implementation of projects worth \$300,000 based on programs aimed at prevention, as a measure against drought, dust storms and temperature rise, as a measure against the rise of temperature, "green covers" on a total area of 600,000 hectares have been shown as important tasks.

As the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy draws attention to these urgent issues, we, as citizens of this country, as well as being concerned about the environment, are willing to fulfill these tasks, and we must work diligently for the prosperity and well-being of our country and the future of our children. The introduction of these chapters and sections related to ecology in the state strategy has greatly pleased the industry workers like us. The high attention to ecology in every lecture and speech of our head of state encourages us to act more energetically. In the pre-election program of the Environmental Party of Uzbekistan, elimination of the above environmental problems and expansion of green areas were defined as the most priority tasks.

Methodology

in our country. But the problem of desertification due to water scarcity is more dangerous than the rest.

And climate change is helping to exacerbate this environmental threat. 80% of the territory of Uzbekistan consists of deserts and steppes, very sensitive ecological systems. Due to the effects of climate change, the amount of rainfall varies and the resulting floods lead to increased soil erosion. The tragedy of the island increased the continentality of the climate, as a result of which summer days became more dry and, on the contrary, frosty days of winter increased. The number of days with air temperature of 40 degrees and above doubled on the island coast. If in 1960 the sea level reached 53.52 m, in 1996 this figure was 35.48 m. In the dry part of the sea, the Orolkum desert was formed on an area of 5 million hectares. From time to time, strong storms appear here, and millions of tons of salt are carried by the wind, causing serious damage to the health of the people living in the northwestern regions of the country. Salt plumes extend to 400 km, and the radius of influence of sand and salt storms reaches 300 km. From this place, up to 100 million tons of sand are blown into the air and spread over hundreds of kilometers every year. The desertification of the island region has led to the degradation of land resources and a decrease in the quality of natural pastures. In November 2018, the UN Trust Fund was established in the region to address the environmental problem in Moscow. This created an opportunity to implement projects aimed at improving the living conditions of the population living in the area by attracting donor funds. According to the results of the visit of the President of Uzbekistan Sh. In November 2018, the 2-year State program of the Republic of Karakalpakstan was accepted in Mirziyoyev Moynaq district. According to him, it is planned to implement 793 projects worth 1.5 billion US dollars.

Our country is an agro-industrial country based on irrigated agriculture. Although the area of irrigated land in the Republic is 4.3 million hectares, agricultural products, that is, irrigated land, are of great importance in meeting the needs of 90-95% of the population. Currently, of the 4.3 million hectares of irrigated land in the republic, 2.0 million hectares (46.7%) have varying degrees of salinity. In particular, 1 million 324 thousand hectares (30.9%) of land is slightly saline, 570 thousand hectares (13.3%) of land. moderately saline and 105.5 thousand hectares (2.5%) are highly saline¹. This requires a more in-depth look at the issue at this time.

The main part

During the years of independence, measures were developed and implemented in the field of ensuring important organizational, socio-economic, legal and environmental security. The implemented measures made it possible to reduce the level of air pollution, improve the condition of the main open water bodies, reduce the use of pesticides, improve the structure, involve international organizations in solving agricultural and national environmental problems, and improve the atmosphere. By comparing these actions, we can see how much we have prevented environmental threats:

¹ Information on www.agro.uz/uz/information/reports

The primary area of focus is Legislation and Public Policy. Effective legislation and public policy are important in solving environmental problems. For this, it is necessary to improve environmental laws, implement state programs and projects.

During the years of independence, more than 40 legal and about 1000 legal documents were adopted. Among them, "On Nature Protection" (1992), "Water and Water Use" (1993), " On Protection of Atmospheric Air" (1996), " "On Water Conservation", "Wildlife and Its Wise Use" (1997), "On Forest" (1999), "On Subsoil Resources" (2002), "On Public Control" (2018), and the Land Code (1998)) can be cited. In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Nature Protection" dated December 9, 1992 defined the role of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the state policy on nature.

The next important aspect is international cooperation. International cooperation is also important in solving environmental problems. For this, it is necessary to cooperate with international organizations and other countries, to jointly implement environmental projects.

During these times, environmental protection in the field of the Republic of Uzbekistan ratified a number of international conventions and became part of relevant protocols for their development. Currently, the Republic of Uzbekistan occupies a leading position among the member states in the field of environmental protection and use of natural resources. 11 international conventions and 7 multilateral agreements and memoranda can be cited as proof of this. GKE is responsible for the implementation of 6 of these conventions, of which 4 are related to the protection of biological diversity, 2 - to the protection of the ozone layer and transboundary transit of hazardous waste. To date, the Republic of Uzbekistan has fulfilled 99.9% of its obligations specified in the conventions and international protocols. This includes the Vienna Convention and the Montreal Protocol, so this fact is given separately. Special recognition by the UN Secretariat for the Protection of the Ozone Layer is worthy of distribution. In 1995, Uzbekistan ²ratified the UN Convention to Combat Desertification . Uzgidromet was elected as the responsible body for the fight against desertification. The main obligations of Uzbekistan under the Bonn Convention are to ensure the protection of migratory species of wild animals. In this regard, cooperation with the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), the International Union for Conservation of Nature, the International Wildlife Fund, the World Crane Fund and other international organizations have been successfully completed. On the basis of the decision of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan in August, projects were implemented only in 2017 within the framework of the Basel Convention "On Transboundary Control of Hazardous Waste Transportation and Their Disposal". This was done in order to establish a comprehensive system of household waste management in the city.

Economic factors are also important in solving environmental problems. For this, it is necessary to implement environmentally friendly technologies, use of renewable energy sources, waste processing and measures to reduce them. In this regard, a number of measures were implemented in the following decades of independence. One of them is the "Environmental protection" program in 2008-2012, with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 212 of September 19, 2008, 376.14 billion soms, 427.79 million US dollars and 504.4 thousand euros were allocated to this program. was spent on the implementation of the program. According to the program, the amount of pollutants was reduced due to the conversion of 145,500 cars to gas fuel. Nitrogen oxide emissions disposed of at the facilities of Uzkiyosanoat JSC decreased by 3.5 million tons. HPP was built and commissioned. Land reclamation of Hisar reservoir and about 86 thousand hectares of agricultural crops was improved. "ManSapitaS.P.S" company in Bahrain, Ohangaron and Parkent districts, South "SejinG&E" company invested 50 million in Korea, Jizzakh and Syrdarya regions, 50 million in Austria, Germany and Azerbaijan "Enelarchitestural" consortium (investments were established on August 20, 2009). .

² National report on the state of environmental protection and use of natural resources in the Republic of Uzbekistan (Tashkent, 2006

Above we have considered a number of policies carried out by our state. Now, based on these, let's comment on our proposals, emphasizing two more important aspects:

No matter how many laws and various projects we create to solve environmental problems, we must not forget that he is a driving force. Therefore, it is important to increase the knowledge and skills of the population in understanding environmental problems and solving them. For this purpose, it is necessary to strengthen environmental education in schools and universities, to promote environmental awareness through mass media. It is necessary to prepare various short films and cartoons for children that clearly show environmental disasters and, most importantly, to teach people that environmental problems are serious and that solving environmental problems is not the responsibility of any organization or party, but of the entire nation. Only then, we can assume that citizens will take this issue seriously and increase their social activity in this field. This, in turn, requires creating as many eco-friendly projects as possible and spreading such projects among people by encouraging volunteers. In this way, the opportunities for us to achieve social activity of the population and return high indicators will be opened.

Summary

No matter how hard a person tries, he remains powerless before the laws of nature. However, taking measures to minimize or prepare for potential disasters will not fail to show positive effects on people in the future. Therefore, it may be true that we cannot stop environmental disasters or desertification, but it is within our power to solve the problem at least a little or to save the available resources as much as possible. The projects and initiatives carried out in our country since the period of independence are aimed at this, and every year a certain amount of growth is achieved in this field. But various environmental problems have not stopped showing their new manifestations. Raising the struggle with environmental problems to a new level is in the hands of young people. Because today's youth is not in a situation where they look back. It is no longer a secret that especially the youth of Central Asia will face enormous environmental problems in the coming decades. Therefore, it is very important to pay attention to the social factors of solving environmental problems, to educate young people with love for the environment and to teach them to protect it. Taking this into account, it is not only the duty, but also the duty of each young generation to confront environmental problems and protect nature.

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